

Software Version	: 6.3.1.0504	Date	: 12/5/2006 8:18:11 PM
Operator	: FQSISAL	Sample Name	: B
Sample Number	: Split2Au20	Study	:
AutoSampler	: BUILT-IN	Rack/Vial	: 0/8
Instrument Name	: CLARUS 500	Channel	: A
Instrument Serial #	: None	A/D mV Range	: 1000
Delay Time	: 0.00 min	End Time	: 20.00 min
Sampling Rate	: 12.5000 pts/s		
Sample Volume	: 1.000000 ul	Area Reject	: 0.000000
Sample Amount	: 1.0000	Dilution Factor	: 1.00
Data Acquisition Time	: 12/2/2006 7:55:26 PM	Cycle	: 8

Raw Data File : C:\CLARUS 500\Estancia Invest Microalgas M Sacritan Jun 2023\062623B_Split2Au20.raw
 Result File : c:\clarus 500\estancia invest microalgas m sacritan jun 2023\062623b_split2au20.rst [Editing in Progress]

Inst Method : C:\CLARUS 500\metodos\EMAG Met 20min Split2 Auto from C:\CLARUS 500\Estancia Invest Microalgas M Sacritan Jun 2023\062623B_Split2Au20.raw

Proc Method : C:\CLARUS 500\metodos\EMAG Met 20min Split2 Auto from c:\clarus 500\estancia invest microalgas m sacritan jun 2023\062623b_split2au20.rst [Editing in Progress]

Calib Method : C:\CLARUS 500\metodos\EMAG Met 20min Split2 Auto from c:\clarus 500\estancia invest microalgas m sacritan jun 2023\062623b_split2au20.rst [Editing in Progress]

Report Format File: C:\CLARUS 500\metodos\EMAG Met 20min Split2 Auto.rpt

Sequence File : C:\CLARUS 500\secuencias\062623-_.seq

DEFAULT REPORT

Peak #	Time [min]	Area [$\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$]	Height [μV]	Area [%]	Norm. Area [%]	BL	Area/Height [s]
1	0.843	807988.50	957991.70	62.55	62.55	BV	0.8434
2	0.926	483025.43	347244.51	37.39	37.39	VB	1.3910
3	7.188	51.35	38.96	0.00	0.00	BB	1.3181
4	9.112	348.71	263.15	0.03	0.03	BB	1.3251
5	9.341	80.51	60.45	0.01	0.01	BB	1.3318
6	10.926	36.00	27.57	0.00	0.00	BB	1.3058
7	11.089	71.02	51.41	0.01	0.01	BB	1.3813
8	11.151	43.06	30.54	0.00	0.00	BB	1.4097
9	11.483	61.53	43.85	0.00	0.00	BB	1.4035
10	12.030	54.31	36.78	0.00	0.00	BB	1.4769
		1291760.43	1.31e+06	100.00	100.00		

Missing Component Report

Component Expected Retention (Calibration File)

All components were found